

EFFECTIVENESS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF DRUG-FREE WORKPLACE PROGRAM IN THE PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE -POLICE REGIONAL OFFICE 12 (PNP - PRO 12) AND BUREAU OF JAIL MANAGEMENT AND PENOLOGY REGIONAL OFFICE 12 (BJMP - RO 12)

Joni Ressa L. Layso ¹, Sheruel G. Matalandang, DiSDS ²

Mindanao State University–Graduate Studies, General Santos City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the extent of implementation and the level of effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) in two key law enforcement agencies in Region 12: the Philippine National Police - Police Regional Office 12 (PNP PRO 12) and the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology - Regional Office 12 (BJMP RO 12). Employing a descriptive correlational research design, the study involved 370 randomly selected respondents from both agencies. A validated and reliable researcher-made questionnaire, grounded in Dangerous Drugs Board Regulation No. 13, Series of 2018, was used to collect quantitative and qualitative data. The DFWP was assessed based on three core components: (1) advocacy, training, and education; (2) conduct of drug testing; and (3) monitoring and evaluation. Effectiveness was measured in terms of workplace safety, employee productivity, service excellence, and strengthened working relationships. Results indicated that while the program is generally implemented, variations exist in the degree and consistency of application across the two agencies. A statistically significant relationship was found between the extent of implementation and the perceived effectiveness of the DFWP, as determined using Spearman Rank Correlation at a 0.05 significance level. Qualitative responses highlighted best practices and challenges in program execution, such as leadership support, resource limitations, and organizational culture. The findings underscore the need for enhanced policy

enforcement, continuous monitoring, and the integration of holistic approaches to sustain a drug-free, productive, and safe workplace environment in the public sector.

Keywords: *Drug-Free Workplace Program, law enforcement, implementation, effectiveness, PNP PRO 12, BJMP RO 12*

INTRODUCTION

Workplaces have become our second homes, where people spend around 90,000 hours of their lives (Gettysburg College, 2007). This significant time allocation emphasizes the importance of ensuring that work environments are safe, healthy, and free from the influence of drugs. Globally, drug use continues to rise, with an estimated 292 million users as of 2022, and about 1 in every 81 individuals suffering from a drug-related disorder (UNODC, 2024). In the Philippines, the Civil Service Commission mandates a 40-hour work week for government employees, highlighting the critical need for effective workplace policies to protect employee welfare. Substance abuse remains a major issue, with a substantial portion of drug rehabilitation admissions being employed individuals (DDB, 2021). In response, the Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB) and the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) have mandated the establishment of Drug-Free Workplace Programs (DFWPs) in both the public and private sectors. These policies, notably DDB Regulation Nos. 2 (2004) and 13 (2018), aim to institutionalize drug testing, education, advocacy, and monitoring to ensure that all workplaces—especially in government—are drug-free.

Law enforcement agencies like the PNP and BJMP play a crucial role in the country's criminal justice system and are expected to be models in upholding drug-free policies. However, despite nearly two decades of DFWP policy existence, drug use still persists among government employees, suggesting potential gaps in implementation and effectiveness. This study is essential because it addresses the lack of local empirical evidence on the actual implementation and impact of DFWPs—particularly in law enforcement settings such as PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. By evaluating how these programs are implemented and how effective they are in enhancing workplace safety, productivity, and employee relationships, the research can offer critical insights for policy enhancement and more robust enforcement of drug-free workplace standards.

Related Literature

The Drug Situation in the Philippines and Region 12

The drug problem in the Philippines has escalated into a national crisis, affecting public health, safety, and socioeconomic stability. Methamphetamine hydrochloride or "shabu" remains the most abused drug, with international syndicates such as the African Drug Syndicates, Chinese Drug Syndicate, and the Mexican Sinaloa Drug Syndicate playing significant roles in trafficking (PDEA, 2016; PDEA, 2023). By 2020, 32.5% of barangays were drug-affected, and four million drug users were reported nationwide.

Region 12 reflects similar trends, where shabu and marijuana dominate illegal drug use. Drug trafficking in the region leverages nautical highways and various land routes, making interdiction difficult. The price of drugs varies depending on the proximity to supply routes (PDEA RO 12, 2024). Despite high-profile surrenders during the Duterte administration, enforcement challenges such as logistical limitations hinder PDEA RO12's operational success (Llano, 2012).

Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP)

The DFWP is a preventive measure intended to eliminate substance abuse in work environments. It emphasizes education, testing, and rehabilitation to promote health and safety. Inspired by the U.S. Drug-Free Workplace Act of 1988, which mandates such policies for federal contractors (U.S. Department of Labor, 2019), similar strategies have been adopted globally. Frone (2003) and Macdonald et al. (2019) argue that comprehensive DFWPs, combining education, deterrence, and support services, reduce workplace substance abuse. In the Philippines, these initiatives are institutionalized through DDB Regulations No. 2 (2004) and No. 13 (2018), and CSC Resolution No. 1700653 (CSC, 2017; DDB, 2004, 2018).

Implementation and Challenges

Implementation of DFWPs in the Philippines varies. While drug testing is widely performed, critical components like employee education, post-testing interventions, and program monitoring are often underdeveloped (Villanueva, 2018; Lacson & Rivera, 2020). In contrast, U.S. agencies have integrated training, sanctions, and leadership into their DFWPs with better results (Anderson & Bokemeier, 2011). The effectiveness of local programs hinges on leadership support and sufficient resources (Santos, 2019; Bennett, 2018).

Core Components of DFWP

Advocacy, Training, and Education

Training and education enhance awareness, shift behavior, and align workplace practices with national drug policies. Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, Knowles' (1984) Adult Learning Theory, and Mezirow's (1991) Transformative Learning Theory provide the foundation for behavior change. Programs that continuously educate personnel, especially through advocacy and multimedia efforts, help reinforce drug-free norms (Carter & Green, 2020; Bennett & Lehman, 2001). IEC materials and regular orientations are effective tools for sustaining awareness (DDB, 2018; DOLE, 2003).

Drug Testing

Random and pre-employment drug testing serves as a preventive and disciplinary tool. It is supported by Deterrence Theory (Becker, 1968) and the Public Health Approach (National Institute on Drug Abuse, 2021), which position drug testing as both a behavioral

deterrent and health intervention. Research supports the effectiveness of well-implemented drug testing in reducing drug use and absenteeism (Frone, 2013; Johnson & Patel, 2017; Bennett & Lehman, 2001). However, implementation faces logistical, ethical, and financial hurdles (CSC, 2017; Reyes & Ferrer, 2019).

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E)

M&E frameworks, including Results-Based Management and Utilization-Focused Evaluation, enable continuous assessment of DFWP outcomes (OECD, 2002; Patton, 2008). Programs with regular M&E show better alignment with institutional goals and enhanced effectiveness (Roman & Blum, 2002). However, government agencies often lack the budget and technical expertise for proper evaluation (Reyes & Ferrer, 2019). Strong leadership involvement in M&E activities improves legitimacy and compliance (Robinson et al., 2017).

Measures of DFWP

Workplace Safety

DFWPs significantly improve workplace safety by minimizing risks associated with substance use. They foster shared responsibility and reduce injury and absenteeism rates (Frone, 2013; Cole, 2017). Safety-focused leadership and compliance reinforce these outcomes (Robinson et al., 2017; Bennett & Lehman, 2001). Government regulations mandate implementation in safety-sensitive positions (DDB, 2018).

Productivity and Service Excellence

Substance abuse impairs employee performance, decision-making, and attendance. DFWPs improve these outcomes through policy-driven behavior change and engagement (Frone, 2003; Hartwell et al., 2004). Job satisfaction and motivation also increase in supportive, drug-free environments (Christian et al., 2011; Artz & Kim, 2019; Heskett et al., 1994).

Strengthened Working Relationships

Strong workplace relationships, essential for organizational health, are bolstered by DFWPs. Substance-free environments promote trust and collaboration (Frone, 2013; Lencioni, 2008; Hamid et al., 2019). Clear, fairly enforced policies reduce tension and improve communication (Robinson et al., 2017). When DFWPs are integrated into broader wellness initiatives, interpersonal relationships and workplace climate also improve (Hartwell et al., 2004; Christian et al., 2011).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is depicted in the schematic representation below. As illustrated in Figure 1, the Input box refers to the variables that cause the

problem. It identified two variables: the components and measures of the Drug-Free Workplace Program. Additionally, the diagram shows the connection between the independent and dependent variables.

The Conceptual Framework illustrates how the extent to which Advocacy, Training, Education, Drug Testing, and Monitoring and Evaluation are implemented as components of the DFWP may directly affect the program’s effectiveness in terms of workplace safety, service productivity and excellence, and working relationships within the organization.

Significance Of The Study

The anti-drug law mandates that every workplace implement a program that will deter the use and abuse of illegal drugs to ensure the safety of the entire organization. The implementation of a drug-free workplace in an organization generally aims to provide a safe and healthy working environment for its employees, away from the influence of substances such as illegal drugs, alcohol, and smoking. Drug demand reduction programs play a critical role in proactively preventing the initial drug use of a person that may eventually lead to abuse. The conduct of this study will contribute to the existing literature on the implementation of drug-free workplace programs and how they affect workplace safety, employees’ productivity and service excellence, and strengthened working relationships in the organization. Though government agencies already have programs to prevent substance abuse, this will measure the extent of implementation and effectiveness of such programs, particularly in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. The study’s results will also help the policy-making and law enforcement bodies tasked with monitoring the program’s implementation, such as the DDB and PDEA, to know how to intensify the implementation and craft more comprehensive policies and programs in the campaign for healthier and safer workplaces.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of effectiveness and extent of implementation of the drug-free workplace program of PNP and BJMP in Region 12. Specifically, it answered the subsequent questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Age
 - 1.3. Educational Attainment
 - 1.4. Civil Status
 - 1.5. Years in Service
2. What is the extent of implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 under the following components:
 - 2.1. Advocacy, Training and Education
 - 2.2. Conduct of Drug Testing
 - 2.3. Monitoring and Evaluation
3. What is the level of effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 under the following measures:
 - 3.1. Safety in the Workplace
 - 3.2. Productivity and Service Excellence
 - 3.3. Strengthened Working Relationships
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness and the extent of implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12?
5. What are the best practices and challenges encountered in the implementation of DFWP in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12?

Hypothesis

Based on the aforementioned statements of the problem, this study tested this hypothesis:

- Ho There is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation and the level of effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used the descriptive–correlational survey method of research design in collecting data from the respondents, which aimed to identify the level of effectiveness and extent of implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of the Philippine

National Police - Police Regional Office 12 and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Regional Office 12, as well as its effect on the safety, productivity, and service excellence, and strengthened working relationships in the organization. Quantitative and qualitative methods of gathering the data were employed.

Locale of the Study

The research locale for this study included the Regional Offices of the selected Law Enforcement Agencies in Region 12, namely the Philippine National Police (PNP) and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP). The southernmost and fifteenth most populous city in the Philippines, General Santos (formerly Dadiangas), is home to PNP Police Regional Office 12. Although it is geographically located within the province of South Cotabato, it is run independently of it and serves as the regional hub for industry and commerce in the region.

BJMP Regional Office 12 is located in the southern region of central Mindanao, in the province of South Cotabato. It shares borders with Sultan Kudarat to the north and west, Sarangani to the south and northeast, Davao del Sur to the far northeast, and Sarangani Bay to the southeast. Its total land area is 3,935.95 square kilometers, or 1,519.68 square miles. South Cotabato consists of one component city and ten (10) municipalities. Although traditionally grouped with the province, General Santos, a highly urbanized city, is run separately.

Although these government agencies are located in General Santos City and South Cotabato, their jurisdiction and duties extend throughout the newly reorganized region, which includes the provinces of North Cotabato, South Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, and Sarangani, as well as the cities of General Santos, Koronadal, Tacurong, Kidapawan, and Cotabato.

Figure 3. Pictures of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 Regional Offices

Source: <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1005067> and BJMP RO 12

Respondents of the Study

The study respondents included regular employees or personnel from the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP), the Philippine National Police (PNP), and Regional Offices in Region 12. They were chosen to measure the effectiveness and extent of the Drug-Free Workplace Program implementation in their respective offices.

For this study, 370 employees from the said law enforcement agencies were randomly chosen as respondents. These government employees comprised five (5) personnel in each office that are part of the DFWP Assessment Team and Technical Working Group, 300 personnel from the PNP PRO 12, and seventy (70) personnel from BJMP RO 12. The numbers of respondents per office are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS

Description	Respondents
DFWP Assessment Team/Technical Working Group	
▪ PNP PRO 12	5
▪ BJMP RO 12	5
Regular Employees	
▪ PNP PRO 12	295
▪ BJMP RO 12	65
TOTAL	370

Sampling Technique

The study employed a random sampling technique to determine the number of respondents. In determining the number of respondents, the researcher applied Cochran's formula with a confidence level of 95% or 0.05 margin of error, 5% precision, and a variability of 0.5. The computation was based on the total number of employees of the BJMP RO 12 (≈ 950) and PNP PRO 12 ($\approx 7,500$). Using Cochran's formula, the computed sample size is based on the estimated population for BJMP 12 and PNP PRO 12, which is $8,450 \approx 370$. In conducting research involving a total estimated population of 8,450 personnel from the BJMP RO 12 and the PNP PRO 12, it is imperative to determine a sample size that ensures statistical reliability and representativeness. For this purpose, Cochran's formula was applied and widely used for large populations in social science research (Cochran, 1977). The first sample size was determined to be 384, corresponding to a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Since the population is finite, a correction was applied using the finite population formula, yielding a final sample size of 370 respondents. This approach aligns with best practices in quantitative research, where sample sizes must be sufficiently large to ensure the generalizability of findings (Creswell, 2014). In the Philippine context, such methodology has been consistently utilized in governance and public administration research to inform evidence-based policy-making (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2011). By using Cochran's formula and adjusting for a finite population, the study ensures methodological rigor and relevance in examining issues within these law enforcement agencies.

Data Gathering Instruments

For the regular employees of BJMP 12 and PNP PRO 12, a researcher-made survey questionnaire based on the DDB Regulation No. 13, series 2018, was verified by competent individuals with a history of success in research and public administration. The researcher also tested the reliability and validity of the survey questionnaires used for this research study. The questionnaire has been divided into three (3) sections. The demographic profile of the participants was collected to determine the socioeconomic background of the study respondents, including age, sex, educational attainment, civil status, and years of service.

The first part of the questionnaire focused on the level of implementation of the DFWP in their respective agencies. It was further subdivided into four sub-parts: the components of the DFWP: 1) advocacy, training, and education; 2) drug testing program; and 3) Monitoring and Evaluation.

The following rating scale was used to measure the level of implementation:

Numerical Rating	Verbal Description
4	Fully Implemented
3	Implemented
2	Partially Implemented
1	Not Implemented

The second part of the questionnaire emphasized the effectiveness of the DFWP in the agency in terms of safety in the workplace, productivity of employees, service excellence, and working relationships between the employees. The following rating scale was used to determine the effect of the program:

Numerical Rating	Verbal Description
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Neutral
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

The third part of the questionnaire included open-ended questions specifically for the DFWP Technical Working Group and Assessment Team to gather data on the lived experiences and perceptions of the participants in this study. Likewise, the third part included questions on the experiences, best practices, and challenges the organizations have encountered before and after implementing the Drug-Free Workplace Program and soliciting suggestions and recommendations for the successful conduct of Drug-Free Workplace Programs in other offices or agencies. The Likert Scale was employed in the analysis of the results. Likert scale items were created using composite scores and analyzed using an interval measurement scale (Likert, 1932).

In the discussion of the results, the following interpretation was applied as patterned in the study conducted by Eduardo and Gabriel (2017). In terms of the extent of implementation of the DFWP and its components in the PNP and BJMP in Region 12, the following scale was used in the analysis of the result after obtaining the mean as the statistical measurement:

Numerical Rating	Range	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4	3.5 – 4.00	Fully Implemented	The components of the DFWP are fully implemented in the organization.
3	2.50 – 3.49	Implemented	The components of the DFWP are implemented in the organization.
2	1.50 – 2.49	Partially Implemented	The components of the DFWP are partially implemented in the organization.
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Implemented	The components of the DFWP are not implemented in the organization at all.

The second indicator in the questionnaire is the evaluation of the effectiveness of the DFWP in the organization in terms of safety in the workplace, productivity of employees, service excellence, and working relationships between the employees.

The following measure was used in the analysis of the result after obtaining the mean as the statistical measurement:

Numerical Rating	Range	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	The employees strongly agree that the DFWP affects workplace safety, productivity, service excellence, and working relationships.
4	3.60 – 4.19	Agree	The employees agree that the DFWP affects workplace safety, productivity, service excellence, and working relationships.
3	2.60 – 3.59	Neutral	The employees cannot determine if the DFWP affects workplace safety, productivity, service excellence, or working relationships.

2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree	The employees do not agree that the DFWP affects workplace safety, productivity, service excellence, and working relationships in the organization.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	The employees strongly disagree that the DFWP affects workplace safety, productivity, service excellence, and working relationships in the organization.

Representatives from the PNP, PDEA, and the BJMP evaluated the research instrument expertly to guarantee its construct validity and content. Each expert used ten criteria to evaluate the instrument, including scale appropriateness, item suitability and relevance, direction clarity, item adequacy, organization, objectivity, comprehensiveness, data generation, and purpose attainment. Every item received the highest possible rating of five stars from all experts. The Item-Level Content Validity Index (I-CVI) for each criterion was 1.00, signifying complete consensus among experts. The Scale-Level Content Validity Index (S-CVI) was determined using the universal agreement method (S-CVI/UA) and the average method (S-CVI/Ave), yielding a value of 1.00 for each method. The findings indicate the instrument's strong content validity and appropriateness for the research (Polit & Beck, 2006). The reliability of the survey questionnaire was also assessed.

A pilot study involved 30 respondents, with 15 participants from each agency. The researcher assessed reliability through Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a result of 0.96, which signifies excellent internal consistency. Cronbach's Alpha functions as a reliability coefficient, indicating the extent of positive correlation among items in a set. A value greater than 0.70 is generally considered acceptable, while a value above 0.90 is classified as excellent (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). A value of 0.96 indicates that the questionnaire demonstrates high reliability in measuring the intended construct.

Data Gathering Procedures

In gathering data for the study, approval and permission were sought first from the Dean of the Graduate School (GS) of Mindanao State University. Letters of permission to conduct the study were sent to the Regional Directors and/or Heads of Offices of the Philippine National Police - Police Regional Office 12 and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Regional Office 12, ensuring that the results of the survey and the identity of the respondents are treated with utmost confidentiality. The proponent also secured signatures and/or approval of the Informed Consent. After securing the approval to conduct the survey, the researcher proceeded with the survey and provided hard copies of the questionnaires to the target offices. A structured Google Form link to the survey questionnaire was also provided to the respondents for easier access and efficient conduct of the data gathering. The questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents after two to four weeks, while the responses of those who responded via the Google form

link were automatically generated through an online Excel form. Encoding, tabulation, and interpretation of data for the study were then conducted.

Figure 5. Flow Chart of Data Gathering Procedure

Statistical Treatment

In statistical treatments, the researcher used both the descriptive tool for the problems that measure the level of effectiveness as well as the extent of implementation and the DFWP. Subsequently, inferential tools were used to measure the significant differences in the program's implementation and effectiveness between the PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. Statistical tools are necessary to interpret data collected and draw conclusions and recommendations (Sirisilla, 2023). To measure the level of implementation of the DFWP components and the effectiveness of its measures, descriptive statistical measurement, specifically measures of central tendency (mean), was used (Trochim, n.d.). In the statistical data treatment, the researcher employed descriptive and inferential statistical tools to analyze and interpret the findings. Descriptive statistics were utilized to address the research problems concerning the extent of implementation and effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Programs. Descriptive tools, specifically measures of central tendency such as the mean, were used to assess the programs' extent of implementation and effectiveness (Trochim, 2006). Numerical and

graphical representations, including tables, charts, and graphs, were applied to summarize and present the data clearly and organized (Durgumahanthi, 2024).

A notable correlation was identified between the extent of implementation and the effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12, utilizing inferential statistics, specifically Spearman Rank Correlation (rs). The significance level for hypothesis testing was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. The SPSS Version was used for all statistical analyses. The researcher could draw significant conclusions and make pertinent recommendations using descriptive and inferential statistical methods to ensure that the data gathered were appropriately interpreted (Sirisilla, 2023). Content analysis, especially thematic analysis, was utilized to code the third section of the questionnaire, which consists of open-ended questions.

Content analysis aims to arrange and extract meaning from the data gathered to arrive at practical conclusions (Bengtsson, 2016). Using these statistical tools, the researcher was able to analyze and evaluate the collected data and provide appropriate interpretations and conclusions that will guide future policy recommendations and decision-making processes aimed at enhancing stakeholders' satisfaction and program implementation.

Scope and Delimitation

The study focused on the level of effectiveness and extent of the implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program in the Philippine National Police and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology in Region 12 in terms of its components: advocacy, education, and training; conduct of drug testing; and monitoring and evaluation, and how these components affect the workplace's safety, employee's productivity and service excellence, and strengthened working relationships in the organization. This study's respondents were limited to the employees and officers of the regional offices of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. It was conducted from April 2024 to May 2025. Those not mentioned are deemed excluded from the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 outlines the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, which include sex, age, educational attainment, civil status, and number of years in service. These variables help contextualize the study and allow for a more comprehensive interpretation of the results, especially considering the respondents are men and women in uniform.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Female	155	41.9
Male	215	58.1
Total	370	100
Age		
51 years old and above	10	2.7
41-50 years old	83	22.4
31-40 years old	152	41.1
30 years old and below	125	33.8
Total	370	100
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree (Tertiary Education)	350	94.6
Doctorate Degree	2	0.5
Master's Degree (Postgraduate Education)	18	4.9
Total	370	100
Civil Status		
Married	217	58.6
Prefer not to say	5	1.4
Single	146	39.5
Widowed	2	0.5
Total	370	100
Year/s of Service		
21 years and above	18	4.9
16-20 years	53	14.3
11-15 years	84	22.7
6-10 years	87	23.5
5 years and below	128	34.6
Total	370	100

The distribution of respondents by sex shows that 58.1% are male and 41.9% are female, as shown in Figure 6. The result implies a male-dominated workforce in the BJMP and PNP organizations surveyed, which aligns with general patterns in uniformed and paramilitary service sectors where male representation typically outnumbers female personnel (Reaves, 2015).

In terms of age, Figure 7 shows that a significant portion of the respondents (41.1%) fall within the 31-40 years old range, making this the most represented age group. This suggests that the workforce is primarily composed of mid-career personnel, who are likely to have accumulated considerable service experience and occupational maturity. Employees in this age bracket typically exhibit high productivity and assume growing responsibilities within the organization (Frone, 2003).

The second-largest age group comprises those 30 years old and below (33.8%), indicating a substantial number of younger or early-career individuals. These employees bring fresh perspectives, energy, and a strong openness to organizational training and transformation. Their presence supports the development of a dynamic and innovative workforce, especially relevant in public safety institutions where adaptability and responsiveness are critical (Reaves, 2015). Meanwhile, 22.4% of respondents belong to

the 41–50 years old age bracket. This group likely includes senior personnel or supervisory staff, reflecting years of experience and potential involvement in leadership and mentorship roles. The remaining 2.7% of the sample consists of personnel 51 years old and above, which is relatively small. This may be attributed to mandatory retirement regulations, the physical demands of the job, and the structured career timeline often associated with uniformed services in the Philippines (CSC, 2017).

The overall age distribution suggests a balanced workforce with a healthy mix of youthful energy and institutional experience. Such a demographic profile may enhance the implementation of programs like the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP), as it combines the receptiveness of younger staff with the wisdom and oversight of more experienced personnel (Bennett & Lehman, 2001).

In terms of educational attainment, Figure 8 shows that the majority of the respondents (94.6%) have completed a Bachelor's degree or tertiary-level education. This high level of academic qualification suggests that the organization upholds educational standards and values formal training as a prerequisite for professional roles. It also reflects the emphasis on intellectual preparedness, discipline, and critical thinking required in the uniformed services. Additionally, 4.9% of the respondents have attained a Master's degree, indicating that a segment of the workforce is pursuing or has achieved advanced academic training. This may correlate with those in higher positions or specialized roles that require deeper knowledge or administrative competence. A very small proportion (0.5%) of the respondents hold a Doctorate, suggesting a rare but valuable presence of expert-level knowledge within the organization.

The educational profile of the respondents portrays a well-educated group of professionals, which enhances the organization's capacity for decision-making, leadership, and effective service delivery. This reflects the high educational attainment among BJMP and PNP personnel, supporting the civil service requirement for tertiary education in uniformed services (Civil Service Commission [CSC], 2017). It also highlights the potential for further academic and professional development among personnel.

Figure 9 shows the civil status of the respondents; the majority of respondents (58.6%) reported being married, while 39.5% identified as single. A small portion of the respondents (1.4%) preferred not to disclose their civil status, and 0.5% indicated that they were widowed. The predominance of married individuals is consistent with the age distribution of the respondents, most of whom are within the 31-40 and 30 years old and below ranges. This reflects a workforce in which family life and professional responsibilities may coincide, potentially influencing factors such as job stability, benefits, housing, and work-life balance (Christian et al, 2011).

The notable proportion of single respondents also points to a segment of the workforce that may be earlier in their personal or professional journey. In uniformed services, civil status often affects administrative considerations such as eligibility for assignments, leave entitlements, and support systems available to personnel (Reaves, 2015; Frone, 2000). Meanwhile, the small number of respondents who are widowed or who prefer not to disclose their status emphasizes the diversity of life circumstances within the workforce. This underscores the importance of inclusivity and sensitivity in demographic profiling and organizational planning (Bennett & Lehman, 2001).

As regards the years in service, Figure 10 shows that a significant percentage of respondents (34.6%) have served for 5 years or less, suggesting a strong presence of

new or relatively recent entrants into the uniformed service. This influx may be attributed to on-going recruitment efforts or the natural attrition resulting from retirement, resignation, or inter-agency transfers, a common trend in personnel-intensive government sectors (Reaves, 2015).

Meanwhile, 23.5% have served between 6–10 years and 22.7% between 11–15 years, indicating that a substantial portion of the workforce has reached mid-career levels. Personnel within this range are likely to have acquired critical operational knowledge and organizational competencies and are positioned for promotion or leadership roles (Frone, 2003). The group with longer tenure includes 14.3% who have served 16–20 years and 4.9% with 21 years or more. The relatively smaller proportion of long-serving members is typical in uniformed services, where structured retirement systems, physical demands, and mandatory retirement policies often lead to workforce turnover by the time personnel reach higher service brackets (CSC, 2017; Bennett & Lehman, 2001).

Overall, the distribution of years in service reflects a balanced organizational structure comprising a blend of recruits, experienced officers, and seasoned veterans. This diversity supports institutional continuity, mentorship, and adaptive capacity, all of which are essential for sustaining operational effectiveness and ensuring smooth implementation of programs such as the Drug-Free Workplace Program (Patton, 2008).

Level of Implementation of the DFWP

Table 2 presents the respondents' evaluation of the extent to which the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) is implemented in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. The assessment includes key components such as Advocacy, Training and Education, Drug Testing Program, and Monitoring and Evaluation.

Table 2. Level of Implementation of the DFWP

Indicator	WM	Description
Advocacy, Training, and Education	3.61	Fully Implemented
Drug Testing Program	3.65	Fully Implemented
Monitoring and Evaluation	3.47	Implemented
Over-all Mean	3.58	Fully Implemented

Among the components, the Drug Testing Program received the highest weighted mean (WM) of 3.65, indicating that this element is "Fully Implemented". This implies that both random and mandatory drug testing procedures are actively practiced. The Advocacy, Training, and Education component follows closely with a WM of 3.61, suggesting a strong commitment to continuous information dissemination and capability-building efforts related to drug prevention.

The Monitoring and Evaluation component garnered a slightly lower WM of 3.47, which falls under the description "Implemented". This suggests that while mechanisms

are in place, enhancements may be needed to improve their consistency or effectiveness. The overall weighted mean of 3.58 confirms that the program is "Fully Implemented," reflecting the strong compliance of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 with the standards set by DDB and the provisions of Republic Act No. 9165. This demonstrates the agencies' commitment to maintaining a drug-free environment and promoting wellness and discipline among their personnel (Dangerous Drugs Board, 2018; Republic Act No. 9165, 2002).

Table 3. Level of Implementation of the DFWP in terms of Advocacy, Training, and Education

Advocacy, Training, and Education	WM	Description
1) There is an orientation conducted on the Drug-Free Workplace Policy.	3.62	Fully Implemented
2) A banner bearing "THIS IS A DRUG-FREE WORKPLACE, LET'S KEEP IT THIS WAY!" is posted on the Office premises	3.58	Fully Implemented
3) Orientation for employees on the effects of illegal drugs and salient provisions of RA 9165 is conducted regularly.	3.65	Fully Implemented
4) The drug-free workplace policy is integrated into the agency's rules and regulations.	3.63	Fully Implemented
5) IEC materials and videos on drug abuse prevention in the workplace are available.	3.60	Fully Implemented
Mean	3.61	Fully Implemented

As shown in Table 3 on advocacy, training, and education, the respondents believe that orientation for employees on the effects of illegal drugs and salient provisions of RA 9165 is conducted regularly ($M = 3.65$), and the drug-free workplace policy is integrated into the agency's rules and regulations ($M = 3.63$) are fully implemented. Also, a banner bearing "THIS IS A DRUG-FREE WORKPLACE, LET'S KEEP IT THIS WAY!" is posted on the Office premises ($M = 3.58$) and is fully implemented. This component achieved a mean score of 3.61, classified as "Fully Implemented." Specific initiatives, such as regular orientation sessions on the DFWP and the effects of illegal drug use, posting of advocacy banners, integration of policy into agency rules, and availability of IEC materials, reflect strong awareness-building efforts.

These practices are essential to creating a preventive and informed workplace culture, as emphasized in government guidelines (DDB, 2018; DOLE, 2003). According to Lalonde's (1974) health framework, informational and environmental support is foundational in promoting behavioral change.

Table 4. Level of Implementation of the DFWP in terms of Drug Testing Program

Drug Testing Program	WM	Description
1) Drug testing is a mandatory requirement for pre-employment.	3.72	Fully Implemented
2) Regular and job-order or contractual employees are subjected to random drug testing at least once a year.	3.65	Fully Implemented
3) Drug testing is conducted by a DOH-accredited facility.	3.59	Fully Implemented
4) The result of the drug test, if positive, is turned over to the Assessment Team for evaluation and referral to treatment and rehabilitation.	3.64	Fully Implemented
5) The drug test result is strictly confidential and shall be attached to the 201 File of the employee.	3.65	Fully Implemented
Mean	3.65	Fully Implemented

Moreover, table 4 shows that the respondents agree that drug testing is a mandatory requirement for pre-employment ($M = 3.72$), regular and job-order or contractual employees are subjected to random drug- -testing at least once a year ($M = 3.65$), and the drug test result is strictly confidential and shall be attached to the 201 File of the employee ($M = 3.65$) are fully implemented. In addition, drug testing conducted by a DOH-accredited facility ($M = 3.59$) is also fully implemented. The computed mean of 3.65 is described as fully implemented. This area received a mean score of 3.65, also "Fully Implemented." Mandatory pre-employment drug testing and regular testing for all employees, conducted in partnership with DOH-accredited facilities, demonstrate compliance with national regulations. Confidentiality of results and formal procedures for handling positive cases reflect ethical handling and adherence to due process (CSC, 2017). These findings support Frone's (2003) view that a clearly defined and enforced testing protocol strengthens employee accountability and workplace discipline.

Table 5. Level of Implementation of the DFWP in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and Evaluation	WM	Description
1) The DFWP Committee ensures the active implementation of the program.	3.51	Fully Implemented
2) The policy is updated about Dangerous Drugs Board Regulation No. 13 series of 2018.	3.50	Fully Implemented

3) The DFWP Committee regularly conducts meetings and evaluates the effectiveness of the policy.	3.44	Implemented
4) There is adequate funding for the implementation of the program.	3.40	Implemented
5) The head of the agency monitors all the activities relative to the implementation of the policy.	3.58	Fully Implemented
Mean	3.47	Implemented

Finally, on monitoring and evaluation, as shown in Table 5, the respondents know that the head of the agency monitors all the activities relative to the implementation of the policy ($M = 3.58$), and the DFWP Committee ensures the active implementation of the program ($M = 3.51$). Meanwhile, there is adequate funding for the implementation of the program ($M = 3.40$). The computed mean of 3.47 is described as fully implemented. With a mean score of 3.47, this component is also classified as "Implemented". While the DFWP Committee appears functional and the agency head is actively monitoring policy implementation, the relatively lower scores on funding availability and regular evaluation meetings suggest operational gaps. These are crucial to the sustainability and responsiveness of the program (OECD, 2002). Regular policy updates based on DDB Regulation No. 13, s. 2018 reflect the agency's effort to stay aligned with national standards. The overall mean of 3.58 affirms that the DFWP is "Fully Implemented" across the surveyed BJMP and PNP offices. The high scores in advocacy and drug testing components reflect compliance-driven efforts, while moderate scores in referral and monitoring indicate areas where program depth and continuity may be strengthened. A well-rounded implementation of the DFWP requires not only procedural adherence but also investment in human recovery and institutional evaluation (Bennett & Lehman, 2001). Generally, the mean of 3.58 means that the respondents have a very high extent of implementation of the establishment and institutionalization of the Drug-Free Workplace Program of PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12.

Effectiveness of Drug-Free Workplace Program Implementation

Table 6 presents the respondents' level of agreement with statements regarding the effectiveness of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) implementation in their agency. The overall weighted mean of 4.58 falls within the "Strongly Agree" category, indicating a high level of perceived effectiveness of the program among personnel.

Table 6. Effectiveness of Drug-Free Workplace Program Implementation

Indicator	WM	Description
1) The drug-free workplace program (DFWP) implementation in our agency made us feel safe in the workplace.	4.59	Strongly Agree
2) The implementation of DFWP contributes to	4.58	Strongly Agree

our productivity and service excellence.		
3) The DFWP implementation strengthens our working relationships inside the organization.	4.58	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.58	Strongly Agree

Table 6 illustrates the perceived effects of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) implementation among employees in the agency. The findings indicate a very high level of agreement among the respondents regarding the positive impact of the program. Specifically, they strongly agree that the implementation of the DFWP has contributed to a safer work environment ($M = 4.59$), enhanced productivity and service excellence ($M = 4.58$), and strengthened interpersonal relationships within the organization ($M = 4.58$). These results collectively yield an overall mean of 4.58, interpreted as "strongly agree," signifying a very high effectiveness level of the DFWP implementation in the workplace.

The first indicator, *"The DFWP implementation in our agency made us feel safe in the workplace,"* received the highest mean score of 4.59. This reflects a strong consensus that the program contributes to enhancing workplace safety. The strong sense of workplace safety reported by employees aligns with prior studies indicating that drug-free workplace programs are instrumental in reducing incidents related to substance abuse, thereby fostering a secure working environment. According to Frone (2013), organizations that implement clear and enforced substance abuse policies experience fewer workplace accidents, lower absenteeism rates, and improved morale among employees. These outcomes are critical in high-functioning environments where employee well-being and occupational safety are paramount. According to Bennett and Lehman (2001), substance use prevention programs play a vital role in fostering a secure and orderly environment, which is particularly critical in uniformed services where personnel safety and discipline are paramount.

Similarly, the statement *"The implementation of DFWP contributes to our productivity and service excellence"* received a mean score of 4.58, demonstrating that respondents view the program as instrumental in improving performance. This is supported by Frone (2003), who found that substance use in the workplace can impair cognitive functioning, decision-making, and productivity, implying that effective drug policies directly impact organizational efficiency. In addition, the enhancement of productivity and service excellence as perceived by respondents supports the findings of Lehman et al. (2012), emphasized that comprehensive DFWPs are associated with improved employee performance and organizational efficiency. By mitigating drug-related impairments, such programs contribute to better concentration, decision-making, and reliability among staff, all of which are essential in sustaining high levels of service delivery.

The third item, *"The DFWP implementation strengthens our working relationships inside the organization,"* also garnered a mean score of 4.58. This suggests that the program promotes trust, professionalism, and team cohesion. Workplaces with clear

substance abuse policies and consistent implementation often benefit from reduced interpersonal conflicts and stronger team dynamics (Christian et al, 2011). Furthermore, the positive impact of the DFWP on working relationships within the organization suggests that the program promotes a culture of mutual respect and accountability. Studies by Bennett and Lehman (2003) argue that DFWPs can enhance workplace cohesion by establishing shared norms and expectations, particularly when coupled with supportive education and counseling services. A drug-free environment reinforces trust and collaboration, which are fundamental components of healthy professional relationships. The consistently high mean scores across all items imply that the DFWP is well-integrated into the agency's organizational culture. This supports the premise that when such programs are effectively communicated and fairly implemented, they not only deter drug use but also become catalysts for broader organizational benefits. As Hartwell et al. (2004) noted, successful DFWPs are those that are perceived by employees as equitable and beneficial, thereby garnering stronger support and compliance.

The data in Table 3 affirm that the Drug-Free Workplace Program implementation has significantly contributed to a safer, more productive, and more harmonious work environment. These findings are corroborated by various empirical studies, underscoring the value of maintaining and enhancing drug-free policies as part of an organization's strategic human resource and occupational safety management. Overall, the results support the conclusion that the DFWP is not only implemented as a compliance mechanism but is also positively perceived by employees as a driver of safety, productivity, and internal collaboration. These findings are in line with the purpose of DDB Reg. No. 13, series of 2018, which emphasizes the importance of a holistic and proactive approach to drug-free workplace initiatives.

Table 7. Relationship between Extent of Implementation and the Level of Effectiveness of DFWP in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12

Variables Correlated	r	r ²	p-value	Extent of Relationship	Remark
The extent of implementation and the Level of Effectiveness of DFWP in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12	.593	.352	.000	Moderate	Significant

The results of the Spearman Rank Correlation (r_s) reveal a moderate positive significant correlation between the level of effectiveness and extent of implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) in both PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12, with $r(370) = .593, p = .000 < .05$. This finding suggests that as the extent of DFWP implementation increases, so does its perceived effectiveness. The computed coefficient of determination indicates that 35.2% of the variation in the level of effectiveness of DFWP can be explained by the extent to which the program is implemented. The remaining 64.8% of the variation may be attributed to other influencing factors, such as

organizational culture, leadership support, employee engagement, or external environmental variables.

This moderate yet statistically significant relationship underscores the vital role of consistent and comprehensive implementation in realizing the intended benefits of workplace policies. As organizations invest in training, awareness campaigns, monitoring systems, and support services aligned with DFWP goals, the outcomes in terms of safety, performance, and employee well-being become more pronounced. Inadequate or partial implementation, on the other hand, may compromise program credibility and hinder long-term effectiveness. These findings are consistent with the study by Roman and Blum (2002), who found that the effectiveness of workplace drug programs is significantly related to how thoroughly and consistently they are implemented across different levels of the organization. Similarly, Bennett and Lehman (2001) emphasized that the fidelity of implementation, particularly the clarity of policy, fairness in enforcement, and access to support services, has a direct impact on employee perceptions of program success. Furthermore, Frone (2013) noted that when DFWPs are institutionalized and not treated as one-time compliance measures, they are more likely to yield sustained improvements in workplace behavior and performance. This supports the current study's implication that greater implementation leads to greater effectiveness.

The fact that 64.8% of the variation in DFWP effectiveness remains unexplained by implementation alone suggests that future research should explore other contributing variables. These may include the role of organizational leadership, employee attitudes toward substance use policies, access to counseling or rehabilitation services, and the socio-economic context of the workplace. Hartwell et al. (2004) argued that multi-faceted approaches integrating health promotion, employee assistance programs, and leadership commitment tend to produce more holistic and lasting impacts in substance abuse prevention. Moreover, the findings suggest that the extent of DFWP implementation is a key determinant of its perceived effectiveness within PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. Organizations seeking to maximize the impact of such programs must, therefore, prioritize consistent, inclusive, and well-communicated implementation strategies. At the same time, consideration of other contextual and organizational factors remains essential in shaping a truly effective drug-free workplace environment.

Best Practices and Factors for Successful Implementation

The successful implementation of a Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) hinges on several key best practices and factors, as identified through thematic analysis. The themes that emerged from the responses reflect the essential components required to foster a drug-free environment and ensure that such a program is sustainable in the long term. The researcher identified three emerging themes.

Strong Leadership Commitment

Strong leadership commitment stands out as a crucial factor, where top-level management plays a pivotal role in enforcing policies and fostering a culture of

accountability. Clear communication of policies, backed by comprehensive and transparent guidelines, ensures that employees understand the expectations and adhere to the program. Leadership support is crucial for the program's success. Clear guidance from top management helps ensure consistent enforcement and employee buy-in.

A recurring theme in both literature and participant responses is the critical role of leadership. Several respondents emphasized the importance of policy clarity and top-level support. One noted that *"The support of the top management is visible and employees accepted it wholeheartedly,"* illustrating that leadership endorsement drives program acceptance and compliance. Another stated, *"The most important factor for the successful implementation of a Drug-Free Workplace Program in BJMP includes strong leadership commitment, clear policies, and consistent enforcement"*, further affirming the need for authoritative backing and guidance. Leadership involvement ensures transparency and accountability and sets a clear standard for personnel conduct. This aligns with Robinson et al. (2017), who argue that leadership is pivotal in creating an environment where policies are respected and enforced.

The BJMP demonstrates strong leadership commitment to the Drug-Free Workplace Program by issuing institutional policies, such as Memorandum Circulars and command directives, which mandate regular random drug testing among jail personnel. This top-down policy implementation shows that the leadership prioritizes a drug-free environment as a matter of operational integrity and public safety. For instance, in BJMP Memorandum Circular No. 2018-009, the leadership ordered the strict enforcement of the Drug-Free Workplace Program. This includes mandatory random drug testing, disciplinary measures for offenders, and the integration of anti-drug abuse policies in personnel training programs (BJMP, 2018).

The PNP also reflects leadership commitment through its Enhanced PNP Internal Cleansing Strategy, which is spearheaded directly by the Chief PNP. This strategy includes a component on anti-drug abuse and emphasizes zero tolerance for personnel involved in illegal drugs. Regular command conferences, surprise inspections, and random drug tests are enforced at the highest level. According to the Philippine National Police (2020), the Internal Cleansing Strategy focuses on prevention, punishment, and rehabilitation, with leadership directly overseeing drug-testing efforts and immediate administrative action against violators. The partnership between the PNP, the Dangerous Drugs Board, and the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) strengthens accountability and transparency in the execution of the Drug-Free Workplace Program.

Education and Awareness Programs

On-going education and awareness campaigns, such as seminars and workshops, are vital for keeping employees informed about the risks of drug abuse and the benefits of a drug-free environment. Respondents identified on-going education and seminars as essential. One respondent answered, *"Conduct seminars and workshops per year regarding drugs and drug test for all employees"* Another echoed this with, *"Constant reminders to the personnel"* and *"Constant and regular information drive about drug*

awareness”, highlighting the value of continuous engagement and reinforcement. Educational initiatives create awareness, reduce stigma, and empower employees with knowledge about the health and legal risks associated with drug use. These efforts are especially effective when incorporated into regular training cycles. This aligns with Carter and Green (2020), who found that continuous education programs are essential in reducing substance abuse in the workplace. Such programs help create a culture of safety and wellness. Continuous education and awareness programs help mitigate substance abuse by providing on-going information to employees about the risks and benefits of a drug-free environment.

The BJMP implements regular drug prevention and awareness seminars and integrates anti-drug education into its training curriculum for both recruits and existing personnel. These programs emphasize the legal, health, and ethical consequences of drug use, helping personnel recognize and avoid risky behaviors. According to the BJMP (2022), part of its Drug-Free Workplace Program includes mandatory drug education sessions conducted in partnership with the Department of Health (DOH) and the Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB). This covers topics on drug dependency coping mechanisms and support systems available to personnel. These sessions also include psychological interventions and peer counseling to reinforce a culture of accountability and wellness.

The PNP promotes education and awareness through its PNP Anti-Illegal Drugs Operations and Education Program (AIDE Program), which is implemented across all regional offices. This program includes lectures, workshops, and symposia focused on substance abuse prevention, particularly targeting recruits during their Public Safety Basic Recruit Course (PSBRC) and in-service personnel through continuing education. The PNP Training Service (2021) reported that all police training institutions are required to conduct drug awareness education in coordination with the PDEA, emphasizing internal discipline and the role of law enforcers in modeling drug-free behavior. This educational initiative is part of a broader internal cleansing effort and supports the PNP’s policy of professionalizing the force.

Regular and Random Drug Testing

Consistent drug testing, including random checks, is seen as an important practice for maintaining a drug-free workplace. It serves both as a deterrent and a means of ensuring adherence to the policy. Regular and random testing was repeatedly mentioned as a deterrent and a mechanism for policy enforcement. Respondents answered *“Random Drug Test every quarter”* and *“random drug testing to personnel and Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL)”*, demonstrating strong grassroots awareness of its necessity. One stated that *“random drug testing” is part of “monitoring and evaluate mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of the program”*. This speaks to its role not only in enforcement but also in on-going program assessment. Johnson and Patel (2017) highlight the importance of random drug testing in preventing and identifying workplace substance abuse. It acts as both a deterrent and a method for ensuring policy compliance (Johnson & Patel, 2017).

The BJMP implements random and mandatory drug testing as part of its internal cleansing and wellness program. This is carried out across regional offices and among personnel at all levels, helping to ensure integrity and compliance. For example, BJMP Regional Office XII conducted unannounced drug testing as part of its standard protocol, reinforcing a zero-tolerance policy for substance abuse among jail personnel. Officers who test positive are subjected to confirmatory testing, investigation, and disciplinary procedures, including dismissal if warranted (BJMP, 2021). This practice ensures consistency in implementation and reinforces trust in the institution's commitment to ethical service.

The PNP conducts surprise and scheduled drug testing as part of its Enhanced Internal Cleansing Strategy, targeting both high-ranking officials and field personnel. This initiative is monitored by the PNP Internal Affairs Service (IAS) and coordinated with the PDEA. According to the PNP Directorate for Investigation and Detective Management (2022), more than 50,000 personnel underwent random drug tests nationwide. The tests are unannounced and cover both operational and administrative units. Those who fail the tests are immediately relieved from duty pending further disciplinary action. This approach supports a culture of integrity and accountability and serves as a visible commitment of leadership to professional standards. The integration of these factors into the organizational culture can significantly reduce workplace incidents related to substance abuse, enhance productivity, and promote employee well-being. Together, these best practices form the backbone of a robust DFWP. They are not only operational measures but also cultural pillars that shape ethical behavior, protect public trust, and sustain internal discipline in law enforcement institutions. Therefore, organizations must prioritize these best practices to ensure the long-term success of the DFWP.

The quantitative results of the study strongly support the best practices identified in the successful implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP). Firstly, strong leadership commitment emerged as a foundation of effective DFWP implementation. This was supported by a high level of agreement from respondents that the heads of agencies actively monitor program activities (WM = 3.58). Respondents emphasized leadership visibility and policy enforcement as essential to success, noting that "the support of the top management is visible and employees accepted it wholeheartedly". This reinforces the idea that leadership sets the tone for accountability and program acceptance. In addition, education and awareness programs were rated as "Fully Implemented" (WM = 3.61). Regular seminars, orientation sessions, and visible advocacy materials, such as drug-free workplace banners, contribute to preventive workplace culture. Respondents affirmed the importance of continuous learning with statements like "conduct seminars and workshops per year regarding drugs and drug tests for all employees." These efforts align with best practices and show strong integration into agency protocols.

Lastly, regular and random drug testing received the highest rating among all components (WM = 3.65). Mandatory pre-employment testing and annual random testing were confirmed to be fully implemented. This reflects a well-institutionalized policy that acts as both a deterrent and a safeguard for workplace integrity. In terms of

perceived effectiveness, respondents strongly agreed that the DFWP contributed to a safer (WM = 4.59), more productive (WM = 4.58), and more cohesive workplace (WM = 4.58). The statistical analysis further confirmed a moderate, significant correlation ($r = .593$) between implementation and perceived effectiveness, emphasizing that the more consistently and thoroughly the program is implemented, the more positively it is experienced by personnel. In summary, the quantitative data affirm that the core best practices, leadership commitment, education, and regular testing, are effectively in place and contribute meaningfully to a positive workplace environment. However, challenges related to monitoring, funding, and cultural sensitivity must be addressed to sustain and enhance the impact of the DFWP.

Challenges Encountered

Based on the responses, several themes emerged around the challenges encountered during the implementation of a Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) in their respective offices. The researcher identified three (3) arising themes using the thematic/content analysis.

Resistance to Change

One of the most recurring challenges was employee resistance to the implementation of the DFWP. Some personnel were hesitant to embrace new protocols, particularly drug testing and stricter policy enforcement, due to fear of punishment or loss of privacy. This hesitancy is consistent with findings from the Monitoring and Evaluation component, which had the lowest weighted mean of 3.47, indicating that while implementation is on-going, there may be inconsistencies or hesitations in compliance. Resistance is a common barrier in workplace change initiatives. Respondents noted that *“some of the barriers encountered were personnel resistance,”* which stemmed from fear of punishment or the disruption of long-standing routines. However, as one respondent shared, *“they were communicated properly,”* highlighting the importance of clear communication and leadership engagement in overcoming such resistance. Kotter (2012) explains that resistance can stem from fear, misunderstanding, or mistrust and must be addressed through transparent communication and inclusive leadership strategies. Overcoming resistance was achieved through clear communication, consistent enforcement of policies, and leadership commitment, which helped integrate the drug-free principles into the workplace culture and routine.

Limited Financial and Human Resources

Several offices reported difficulty in sustaining program activities due to budget constraints. This included challenges funding random drug tests, awareness seminars, and counseling programs, especially in remote or underfunded regions. A common theme among the responses was the challenge of funding regular drug testing, awareness campaigns, and support services,

particularly in resource-constrained areas. Respondents acknowledged that “the cost of the implementation was challenging due to some financial constraints but it was adjusted properly”.

Despite the overall high ratings in the Drug Testing Program (WM = 3.65) and Education and Advocacy (WM = 3.61) components, several responses indicated budgetary constraints affected the depth and consistency of these efforts. One respondent shared, *“The cost of the implementation was challenging due to some financial constraints but it was adjusted properly.”* This supports the idea that although the program is implemented, sustainability and reach may vary due to financial limitations. The relatively lower scores within the Monitoring and Evaluation component (e.g., adequate funding WM = 3.40) further affirm that limited resources remain a significant challenge. This is particularly important considering that these resources are needed to fund not only drug testing but also awareness campaigns and support services. Reyes and Ferrer (2019) assert that financial and logistical limitations are typical challenges in implementing health-related workplace programs. Organizations must adopt creative budgeting and resource-sharing to manage effective program delivery. Limited resources were addressed by seeking external funding, partnerships with agencies like DILG, PDEA, and DOH, and creative budgeting to ensure the program's continuity (Reyes & Ferrer, 2019).

Stigma and Privacy Concerns

The stigma associated with drug use was a major issue. Employees were often reluctant to seek help for fear of discrimination or shame, making it harder to foster a culture of openness and rehabilitation. One respondent shared, *“Limited resources and stigma around seeking help... were overcome through leadership support, continuous education, and access to confidential counseling services.”* Additionally, *“balancing privacy concerns with the need to maintain a safe workplace”* was a delicate task, as another respondent mentioned issue involving the leakage of sensitive information. These concerns underscore the need for stronger information protection mechanisms to build employee trust.

Although drug testing was statistically rated as “fully implemented,” these numbers do not fully capture the emotional and psychological reluctance among personnel. The effectiveness of the program in creating a safe and supportive work environment was highly rated (WM = 4.59), suggesting that where stigma was addressed through education and confidentiality protocols, personnel felt safer and more supported. However, privacy-related concerns persisted, with concerns about the *“leakage of sensitive information.”* This undermines trust in the program and could explain why some personnel remain hesitant to seek help despite the existence of support systems. The implementation of confidential handling of drug test results (WM = 3.65) reflects some progress, but the concerns raised suggest the need for stronger internal data protection practices.

Corrigan and Fong (2014) emphasize that stigma is a critical barrier to participation in workplace wellness and recovery programs. They recommend confidentiality protocols and awareness campaigns to reduce stigma and normalize help-seeking behavior. To combat stigma, organizations emphasized confidential counseling services, ensuring employees could seek help without fear of discrimination. Clear privacy protocols were also established to protect sensitive information. While the DFWP in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 has been widely implemented and positively received, the quantitative results affirm that effectiveness is closely tied to the degree and consistency of implementation.

Similarly, monitoring and evaluation received a lower mean score (WM = 3.47), suggesting room for improvement. Although agency heads are actively involved, limitations were noted in funding and the regularity of committee meetings. This correlates with challenges cited by respondents, such as limited financial and human resources that hinder the continuity and assessment of program effectiveness. The moderate but significant correlation between implementation and effectiveness ($r = .593$) illustrates this relationship. However, the challenges of resistance to change, limited resources, and stigma/privacy concerns remain key factors that influence the program's success on a deeper level.

Conclusions

The implementation of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 is highly effective, with key components such as advocacy, education, drug testing, and monitoring generally classified as "fully implemented." Respondents strongly agreed that the program promotes safety, productivity, and improved workplace relationships. The success can be attributed to strong leadership commitment, regular drug testing, continuous education, and the implementation of best practices consistent with Social Learning Theory, which asserts that individuals acquire behaviors through observation, reinforcement, and modeling. The program prioritizes visible leadership, social influence, and institutional norms, thereby cultivating a workplace culture that promotes, reinforces, and maintains drug-free behavior.

Additionally, the regular and random drug testing protocols, coupled with clear consequences for violations, reflect the principles of Deterrence Theory, which asserts that individuals are less likely to engage in undesirable behavior when they perceive a high certainty of detection and punishment. The study supports this notion, as the presence of strict enforcement measures contributed to employee compliance and accountability. Despite its effectiveness, challenges such as resistance to change, limited resources, and privacy concerns suggest the need for ongoing support and program refinement. Addressing these issues will be crucial for maintaining long-term program credibility, inclusiveness, and impact. Overall, the integration of behavioral and organizational theories into DFWP implementation has contributed to its success, making it a model for promoting discipline and wellness in uniformed services. In conclusion, while the DFWP was generally effective and well-received, its sustained success depends

on reinforcing best practices and addressing the persistent challenges related to change resistance, resource constraints, and stigma.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that sustainability mechanisms be institutionalized to ensure the long-term success and integrity of the Drug-Free Workplace Program (DFWP) in PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12. These mechanisms should include the following:

1. Institutionalization of a Dedicated DFWP Unit or Focal Person

Each regional and local office should designate a permanent focal person or create a dedicated unit responsible for coordinating, monitoring, and evaluating the DFWP. This will help ensure continuity, accountability, and regular updating of policies and practices, considering that uniformed personnel may be reassigned to other units and offices from time to time.

2. Integration of DFWP Funding in Annual Budgets

To address financial constraints, agencies should institutionalize DFWP-related expenses, including testing, education, and support services, into their annual budget proposals. This ensures regular program activities without reliance on ad hoc funding and promotes the sustainability of its regular implementation.

3. Enhanced Confidentiality and Support Systems

Strengthen data protection protocols and create accessible, confidential counseling or referral services to reduce stigma and encourage personnel to seek help without fear of discrimination or breach of privacy. Resistance should be addressed, and behavioral change should be promoted. Reinforce positive behavior and support a culture of accountability through recognition and reward.

4. Periodic Review and Policy Update Mechanism

Establish a mechanism for regularly reviewing the DFWP in line with new regulations, evaluation data, and organizational feedback to ensure that the program remains responsive and effective.

5. Strengthen Inter-Agency Collaboration

Sustain partnerships with the Department of Health (DOH), Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB), and Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) to ensure program alignment with national standards and to access additional resources and technical support. Sustaining the recertification on the Drug-Free Workplace Program Seal established by the Department of Interior and Local Government Regional Office 12 is also recommended.

By embedding these sustainability mechanisms, PNP PRO 12 and BJMP RO 12 can ensure that the DFWP evolves into a long-term institutional commitment, one that reinforces a culture of wellness, discipline, and professionalism in uniformed services.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adheres to the ethical guidelines that the university has established for carrying out research investigations. Respecting the policy of protecting research participants' dignity by guaranteeing their responses' privacy is fundamental to how the study is conducted. All necessary approvals were obtained to guarantee the respondents' voluntary involvement in the study. Under Republic Act No. 10173, also called the Data Privacy Act, respondents' sensitive information, including their profiles, was handled in strict confidence. This was done to maintain their trust in the survey and ensure the security of their personal information.

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